

CHILDHOOD VACCINATION REMINDERS AND ENCOURAGEMENT

AUTHOR: M. FAIRLESS

REVIEW: S. KAGEL, S. HILTON

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RECOMMENDED

Research Report:

Mass Media – Childhood vaccination reminders and encouragement

Author: Morgan Fairless

Review: Samantha Kagel, Sam Hilton

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For questions about the content of this research, please contact morgan@charityentrepreneurship.com. For questions about the research process, please contact Sam Hilton at sam@charityentrepreneurship.com.

Executive summary

Charity Entrepreneurship (CE) fosters more effective global charities by connecting capable individuals with high-impact ideas. In 2023, CE investigated ideas related to social and behavioral change campaigns via mass media. This report discusses the merits of mobile phone reminders and encouragement for childhood immunization.

Millions of children remain unvaccinated every year and go on to suffer fully preventable diseases. For instance, in 2021, around 20% of children in Africa did not receive the BCG vaccine, and close to 30% did not get the third dose of the DTP vaccine.

The intervention proposed in this report is relatively simple, with a proven track record. It provides caregivers with reminders and encouragement about upcoming opportunities to vaccinate their children through mobile phones (either SMS or voice reminders).

High-quality evidence supports using reminders to increase vaccination in children, including several Cochrane and other large meta-analytic reviews.

Despite their usefulness, we understand that reminders are underutilized and that several countries with relatively low vaccination rates have not scaled up their use. Depending on the context, many factors can influence the lack of scale-up of health technologies, with the most likely culprit being a lack of resources and competing priorities, lack of digital health information systems, poor governance, and no advocacy.

Experts reflected a positive outlook for reminder services to bridge the gap in routine immunizations. There were divergent opinions on how these services should be delivered and by whom, such as the private sector or through more holistic non-disease specific approaches.

We conducted a geographic assessment to reach a shortlist of countries where this type of work may be promising: Papua New Guinea, Myanmar, Nigeria, Angola, Philippines, Central African Republic, Guinea-Bissau, Guinea, Madagascar, and Indonesia.

Our cost-effectiveness estimates for this intervention, based on delivery in Angola, were USD 38 and 78 per DALY averted, with the former resulting from considering charity costs alone and the latter including additional costs to the government.

This intervention is tractable, with common barriers - such as access to robust information systems - being surmountable.

Overall, our view is that childhood vaccination reminders and encouragement is an idea worth recommending to future charity founders.

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1 Introduction

Charity Entrepreneurship's (CE) mission is to foster more effective charities worldwide by connecting talented individuals with high-impact ideas to help humans and animals. We achieve this goal through an extensive research process and our nonprofit incubation program. In 2023, our research process focused on social and behavioral change campaigns (SBCC) through mass media.

CE research staff chose childhood vaccination reminders and encouragement as a potentially promising intervention within this category. This decision was part of a six-month process designed to identify interventions that were most likely high-impact avenues for future charity entrepreneurs. The research began by listing around 160 ideas, gradually narrowing them down, and examining them in increasing levels of depth.

We use various decision tools such as group consensus decision-making, weighted factor models, cost-effectiveness analyses, quality-of-evidence assessments, case study analyses, and expert interviews to assess how promising interventions are for future charity entrepreneurs.

This process is exploratory and rigorous but not comprehensive – we did not research all ideas in depth. As such, our decision not to take forward a charity idea to the point of writing a full report does not constitute a view that the idea is not good.

2 Background

2.1 Cause area

The media content we engage with informs, persuades, and entertains us. However, only a handful of organizations worldwide effectively use communication tools to deliver evidence-based, cost-effective solutions to tackle some of the most significant challenges facing the world's poorest people. To rectify this, we identify highly impactful opportunities to deliver social and behavioral change campaigns (SBCC) through mass media.

SBCC delivered to large audiences through mass media can empower people to make better choices about their health and well-being. Messages on the importance of mask-wearing and vaccination during Covid-19 are familiar examples of this potential ([Anwar et al., 2020](#); [Cherry et al., 2021](#); [Chadwick et al., 2021](#)).

SBCC is an (ideally) research-based, systematic approach that utilizes communication strategies to promote positive behaviors and social change among individuals and communities ([Centre for Social and Behavior Change Communication, n.d.](#)). By mass media channels, we refer to large-audience media that (in most cases) is very broadly targeted. We include traditional (radio, television, newspapers) and modern (SMS, voice messages, internet, and chatbots) media. We keep the definition of human well-being broad to encompass health, income, and personal well-being.

The following sections provide an overview of our perspective on the relative value of mass media interventions before going into the specifics of entertainment-led approaches to reduce IPV.¹

Factors in favor

Owing to their vast reach and low costs, well-managed mass media interventions can be extremely cost-effective even if they only manage to change behavior in a small proportion of the general target population ([Bettle, 2023](#)).² Founders Pledge estimates that some mass media interventions can be between four and 32 times as cost-effective at improving people's health and well-being as unconditional cash transfers delivered by GiveDirectly ([Bettle, 2023](#)). Growing mobile phone access among the world's poorest has also led to some of the most significant advances in their health and financial well-being through tools like reminders, mobile health, and mobile money.

¹ For an in-depth treatment of the mass media we recommend Bettle ([2023](#)) and Wakefield et al. ([2010](#)).

² Some large organizations working in this sector include [Development Media International](#), [MTV Staying Alive](#), [Population Foundation of India](#), [Farm Radio](#), and the CE-incubated [Family Empowerment Media](#).

In many low and middle-income countries (LMIC), radio still enjoys audiences of up to 90% of a country's population, reaches most low-income households, and is a highly trusted information source ([Wilhelm & Lorgerie, 2020](#)). The cost of production and dissemination of campaigns remains low in many LMICs. For instance, CE-incubated Family Empowerment Media reached 5.6 million people with its radio programming in North-East Nigeria for USD 440,000 – costing under eight cents of a dollar to reach people multiple times with potentially life-changing information.

Mass media interventions can be of particular value in contexts where providing persuasive information can correct inaccurate information or beliefs with high costs. Generally speaking, these interventions are likelier to succeed when the desired behavior is easy, the message is delivered in a timely fashion, there is a conducive social environment to take the desired action, and the action is attractive ([Behavioral Insights Team, 2014](#)).

Despite the challenges of evaluating mass media approaches (see factors against), several high-quality experimental and observational studies have demonstrated that meaningful population-level behavioral changes can be achieved in areas including healthcare-seeking ([Sarrassat et al., 2018](#)), tobacco cessation, road safety ([Wakefield et al., 2010](#)), and violence against women ([Green et al., 2018](#)).

Factors against

Limited funding, challenges in conducting evaluations, and a general lack of interest have led to the neglect of mass media as a tool.

Mass media is inherently difficult to evaluate using so-called gold-standard methods such as randomized controlled trials (RCTs), partly because it is difficult to randomize media exposure at the population level and because media interventions are inherently prone to spillovers and network effects.^{3,4} Other research methods can be used to establish treatment effects on those exposed to the campaigns. Still, the difficulty of testing using the methods most valued by a large proportion of the development community has likely hampered the spread of this type of work.

Finally, SBCC interventions in general, and mass media interventions in particular, are very context-dependent and require deep formative work to get right. Some experts we interviewed noted that the quality of production and research commonly deployed in development interventions using mass media approaches has often been

³ Some exceptions of experimental or quasi-experimental studies include Sarrassat et al. ([2018](#)), Glennerster et al. ([2022](#)) and Banerjee et al. ([2019a](#)) and Yanagizawa-Drott ([2014](#)).

⁴ In fact, as one interviewee for this research suggested, successful mass media campaigns are attempting to maximize spillovers and network effects by generating conversations and word of mouth about the content they produce ([Naugle Interview](#)).

poor, contributing to weak results. Communication campaigns must be relevant, well-grounded, delivered by trusted messengers, and actionable. These factors are context-dependent, meaning that what works in one neighborhood may not work in another.

2.2 Topic area

Vaccination is among the most important preventative healthcare interventions in the history of medicine, especially when averting childhood illnesses. Successful vaccination has eradicated diseases like smallpox, which existed among humans for thousands of years and killed millions ([World Health Organization, 2023](#)).

According to estimates made in 2012, existing vaccines could avert around 60% of pneumonia deaths and 30% of diarrhea deaths, two of today's largest child-killing illnesses ([Fischer Walker et al., 2013](#)).

The Disease Control Priorities third volume (DCP-3) also notes the well-established cost-effectiveness of vaccination: "Based on 2001 data, the cost per death averted through routine vaccination with the six original antigens in the Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI) was US\$205 in South Asia and SubSaharan Africa; estimated cost per disability-adjusted life year (DALY) averted was US\$7 to US\$16 (Brenzel and others 2006). New vaccines, although more expensive, have also been determined to be cost-effective in Gavi-eligible countries (Atherly and others 2012; Sinha and others 2007)" ([Feikin et al., 2016, p.187](#)).

Table 1: Cost-effectiveness ranges for several vaccines, according to DCP-3 (2012 USD) (source: [Feikin et al., 2016, p. 198](#))

< USD 100/DALY	USD 100 to USD 1036 / DALY	> USD 1036 / DALY
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Original EPI-6: BCG, DTP, measles, polio • Hepatitis B • Pneumococcus, high-child-mortality countries • Rotavirus, high-child-mortality countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Haemophilus influenzae type B • Yellow fever, where endemic • Japanese encephalitis, where endemic • Pneumococcus, medium-child-mortality countries • Meningitis A, where endemic • Rotavirus, medium-child-mortality countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cholera (final price point pending) • Pneumococcus, low-child-mortality countries • Rotavirus, low-child-mortality countries

"Note: EPI = Expanded Program on Immunization; BCG = Bacille Calmette-Guérin; DALY = disability-adjusted life year; DTP = diphtheria, tetanus, and pertussis. For vaccines, cost-effectiveness is sensitive to vaccine price as well as variability in underlying disease burden by country."

Millions of children remain unvaccinated every year and go on to suffer fully preventable diseases. For instance, in 2021, around 20% of children in Africa did not receive the BCG vaccine, and close to 30% did not receive the third dose of the DTP vaccine ([WHO Immunization Data Portal, 2023](#)).

There are several reasons for vaccine under-coverage, mostly varying across contexts, health systems, and types of vaccines. Many theoretical constructs have been proposed to understand the intention to vaccinate and capacity to deliver vaccinations. We think the one proposed in the systematic interpretative literature review by Phillips et al. ([2017](#)) is particularly helpful.

Figure 1: Determinants of vaccine coverage (source: [Phillips et al., 2017, p. 13](#))

* Not in original

Intent to vaccinate relates to the demand from caregivers for vaccines, including behavioral factors such as attitudes toward vaccination, but also whether the caregiver remembers when to vaccinate and is aware of the relative importance of timeliness, among other logistical factors. *Facility readiness* relates to the general supply and ability to deliver vaccination by facilities. *Community access* combines both of the above factors, referring to the (in)ability to carry out the transaction for the vaccine. This latter factor includes barriers and facilitators between intent to vaccinate and facility readiness, such as distance from facilities.

The intervention proposed in this report is a relatively simple one with a proven track record. It provides caregivers with mobile reminders and encouragement (either SMS or voice) relating to upcoming opportunities to vaccinate their children.). High-quality evidence supports using reminders to increase vaccination in children ([Guroi-Urganci et al., 2013](#); [Jacobson Vann et al., 2018](#); [Palmer et al., 2020](#)).

This reminder system can fill some gaps. For instance, a lack of communication between caregivers and healthcare providers/workers has been noted as a barrier to

vaccination in the literature ([Manakongtreecheep, 2017](#)). In a study of vaccination determinants in rural Mozambique, forgetting the day of vaccination was mentioned as a reason for missing vaccines by close to 20% of mothers ([Jani et al., 2008](#), study n=668). A review of the gray literature⁵ also noted that caregivers did not understand the need for more than one dose, when and where to return, and the specific use of different vaccines ([Favin et al., 2012](#)).

Reminders can also play an encouragement role if caregivers have doubts. Experts have noted that messages can be tailored. For instance, they can address mistaken beliefs, reduce fears, and overcome more structural issues like poor outreach to specific oppressed groups.

Despite their usefulness, we understand that reminders are underutilized and that several countries with relatively low vaccination rates have not scaled up their use ([Boum, 2021](#); [Manakongtreecheep, 2017](#)). Depending on the context, many factors can influence the lack of scale-up of health technologies, with the most likely culprit being a lack of resources and competing priorities, lack of digital health information systems, poor governance, and no advocacy ([Bulthuis et al., 2020](#); [Sawadogo et al., 2021](#)). We think a lack of consistent funding and staff resources has contributed to an inability to deploy these at a large scale. Organizations may also fail to prioritize scaling relative to proof-of-concept work (Rogers Interview).

As future sections will note, however, mobile health does attract attention and impetus from funders looking for technological solutions. In the past years, the rise in mobile phone owners has led to the growth of for-profit and non-profit organizations that leverage technology to reach individuals with health services. We are uncertain how to quantify these organizations' space and the remaining gaps.

⁵ Information published in reports outside of traditional publishing (e.g., peer reviewed papers, books).

3 Theories of change

This section provides an overview of our Theory of Change (ToC) for childhood vaccination reminders and encouragement delivered through mobile phones. It gives a broad understanding of our thinking behind how this intervention works.

The ToC for this new organization is a mix of direct delivery and technical assistance. The organization will collaborate with routine immunization sites and health systems (from both governments and nonprofits) to set up and run reminders at scale.

Significant constraints such as low technology development and no/poor data infrastructures, lack of sustainability planning, and uneven financing have challenged past efforts to deploy this ToC. The sense we get from talking to experts and desk research is that reminder interventions, though popular at start-ups and small-scale, rarely reach full and continuous coverage.

Figure 2: Theory of Change

The key assumptions corresponding to each step (i.e., “→”) in the theory of change are:

Scale: *key uncertainty*, *high uncertainty*, *some uncertainty*, *low uncertainty*, *unconcerning*

The organization can set up an effective reminder system. We have confidence that this is feasible. We know of free platforms that support mass messaging, for-profit organizations that can provide this service, and small-and-large-scale charities that have developed their platforms to deliver reminders easily. Technical expertise would be beneficial to innovate solutions that improve usability, especially for frontline health workers.

The organization can successfully partner with routine immunization providers. We are confident that a new organization would provide a valuable service to immunization providers like Ministries of Health or other nonprofits, given that the value proposition would be increased efficacy with very little added work on the provider's side. New nonprofits may still suffer from a lack of credentials to achieve successful partnerships at a large scale. In our experience, CE charities have largely overcome this challenge.

Caregivers receive reminders. Some studies have used surveys to test whether messages are received as intended. Therefore, we know that while achieving 100% success rates is rare, we should be confident that a well-functioning system will have around an 80% + success rate. Phone turnover, lack of battery, and other issues raised by caregivers could be added as part of regular monitoring to understand barriers for people receiving the messages.

In cases where reminders are sent to someone else, like a community member, the caregiver ultimately receives the message. In many cases, the main caregiver (often the mother) will not have a phone but can provide an alternative number (for the father, another relative, their community health worker (CHW)⁶, community leader, or friend). We expect the success rate for the caregiver receiving the message will be lower in these instances.

The content of the reminder is well-understood and well-designed to generate the necessary changes in capabilities, opportunities, and motivation. We are fairly confident that reminders will work as desired based on evidence that suggests strong effects. We think a new organization could also be innovative relative to the standard practice we observed by testing messages and bringing behavioral insights into message design.

We are uncertain about how spam prevalence may affect this intervention. If people are used to getting many spam messages, they may ignore the reminders. One way of alleviating this concern will be to work with trusted parties like ministries of health and mobile phone companies.

Being reminded/encouraged to receive vaccinations is sufficient for the vaccine transaction (i.e., there are no other barriers to access). The evidence base for the effectiveness of reminders is strong, and therefore, we believe that for a subsection of service users, reminders will be sufficient to lead to vaccination. The system can also coordinate between caregivers and healthcare providers to notify of low stocks, upcoming immunization sessions, and non-routine immunization opportunities (success on this part will largely vary across countries, as stakeholders have noted significant practical barriers). Increased communication could build trust and resolve some of the barriers noted in the literature. Reminders are not a silver bullet. New organizations in this space should be cognizant of other significant barriers to vaccination, such as distance and poverty, that reminders are not best suited to address.

⁶ Suvita has mentioned that reminders for CHW or similar stakeholders may be leveraged in other ways, such as making sure that a worker remembers all children they have to provide immunization for during a certain round.

4 Quality of evidence

4.1 Evidence that a charity can make a change in this space

There is strong evidence that SMS reminders can increase vaccination rates in several different contexts.

CE had previously conducted an evidence review on the subject leading to the founding of Charity Science Health (which later merged with Suvita). The process for this evidence review was to update our understanding of the evidence base by searching for newer studies and consolidating several recent systematic reviews and meta-analyses. We discuss the evidence we found below.

Systematic reviews and meta-analysis

We identified nine systematic reviews and meta-analyses through a non-exhaustive review of online sources. Taken as a whole, we believe the systematic reviews provide strong evidence that the intervention could have the desired effects on vaccination rates and timeliness. While studies are often included mostly from HICs, systematic reviews focusing on LMICs have found similar effects. Across different sources, meta-analysis estimates seem robustly similar. The evidence base is heterogeneous and sometimes includes different mediums (such as letters). Most of the evidence pertains to SMS reminders specifically.

Reasons for caution, such as the changing nature of spam messaging and mobile phone ownership, still apply despite the strong evidence in favor. Additionally, these reviews cannot shed light on the potential effects of this intervention on a large scale. It is possible that at significantly low baselines, reminders can have a stronger effect than the reviews find on average. Call reminders have been significantly less studied. We think it is plausible that they could be more effective than SMS reminders in settings with low literacy rates. Still, we have not identified any evidence of this in the systematic reviews, given the fewer interventions focusing on call mechanisms.

Three Cochrane reviews discussed vaccination reminders or similar topics ([Guroi-Urganci et al., 2013](#); [Jacobson Vann et al., 2018](#); [Palmer et al., 2020](#)). They all concluded favorably, noting that reminders can increase attendance to medical appointments or vaccination.

Jacobson Vann et al. (2018) included 55 (n=138,625) RCTs, controlled pre-post, and interrupted time series studies comparing full immunization rates among different

reminder forms. The review found high-quality evidence from six studies (n=7772) comparing text message reminders specifically, identifying that reminders led to increases in vaccination rates of approximately five percentage points (21% vs. 16%, RR: 1.29, 95% Confidence Interval (CI) 1.15 to 1.44). The review also found similar effects for all reminder types with moderate quality evidence (55 studies, n= 138,625). This was the third update of this review since 2002, with stable changes each time.

Palmer et al. (2020) focused on client communication via mobile phones for maternal and child health. The analysis focusing on vaccination attendance in children included ten RCTs (n = 5660). It found low-quality heterogenous ($I^2 > 90\%$) evidence that the reminders increased attendance for vaccinations at six to 12 months and attendance at HIV medical appointments by almost 14 percentage points (78% vs. 64%, RR: 1.21, 95% CI: 1.08 to 1.34). Differences in outcome measures drove heterogeneity.

Guro-Urganci et al. (2013) included eight RCTs (n=6615) comparing attendance rates to healthcare appointments with a message reminder compared to no reminder. The review finds moderate quality evidence of an increase in attendance by approximately ten percentage points (77% vs. 68%, RR: 1.14, 95% CI 1.03 to 1.26).

Other systematic reviews we reviewed reached similar conclusions. Eze et al. (2021) focused on SMS reminders in LMICs exclusively. It included 18 studies (13 randomized and five non-randomized, n=32,712). The study finds that reminders increased vaccination coverage (RR: 1.16; 95% CI 1.10 to 1.21; I^2 90.4%) and identifies that effects were stronger in low-income countries than in richer counterparts. Different estimation approaches to the meta-analysis led to similar results. The evidence from RCTs had a low risk of bias, and the evidence from non-RCTs mostly had a high risk of bias. Yunusa et al. (2021) concluded that “mobile phone reminders, particularly a combination of voice message + SMS and perhaps phone calls, appears to be more effective in enhancing immunization outcomes” (n.p)

Wang et al. (2023) conducted a systematic review of cost-effectiveness analyses, identifying five studies about reminders. It reports that SMS text messaging costs USD 7.9 per additional vaccination case.

It is unclear how the effectiveness of this intervention relates to relative baselines (i.e., whether it has larger effects at lower baselines). However, as seen above, the studies included in these meta-analyses include different baselines and still support the intervention. We interpret the Eze et al. (2021) study as potentially suggesting that results are stronger at lower baselines, but we have not investigated this in depth.

Experimental and quasi-experimental evidence

Our update of the evidence base led to 21 experimental and quasi-experimental studies published between 2015 and 2023. As these studies fed the above reviews, it is not surprising that results similarly support the intervention. Taken together, we view these studies as indicating that we should have confidence that reminders will increase vaccination rates and timely vaccination.

Importantly, the included studies are quite heterogeneous regarding quality and statistical power. Directionally, none suggest any harm to vaccination rates or timeliness. The studies all measure different interventions, including different message content, different choices in number of messages sent, date of message, and context.

The studies also suggest that intervention reminder delivery is feasible at a small and medium scale. Studies that included measures of success rates - when caregivers reported receiving the messages, often cited high rates (e.g., 92% in [Ekhaquere et al., 2019](#); 85% in [Gibson, 2017](#); 96% in [Schlumberger et al., 2015](#)). Studies also reported on the acceptability of messages and views from caregivers positively.

Table 2: Studies included in review

Study, publication status ⁷	Country and setting	Sample	Intervention	Methods [quality score 1 (low) to 3 (high)]	Outcomes ⁸
Bangure et al. (2015) *	Zimbabwe, Urban	304	SMS reminder	RCT [3]	Immunization coverage at 14 weeks - intervention 95% vs control 75% (p < .001).
Eze and Adeleye (2015)*	Nigeria, Urban	905	SMS reminder	RCT [3]	Early receipt of DPT3 - intervention 69% vs. control 60% (OR: 1.468; 95% CI: 1.103 to 1.955; p-value:.009).
Schlumberger et al. (2015) *	Burkina-Faso, Urban	523	SMS reminder	RCT [3]	Immunization completeness for fourth vaccination session - intervention 60% vs 42% (p-value <.001).
Domek et al. (2016) (pilot, not finished yet)*	Guatemala, Urban	321	SMS reminder	RCT [2]	Attendance at third vaccination visit - intervention 84% vs. control 81% (p-value:.69).
Haji et al. (2016)*	Kenya, Rural and Urban	744	SMS reminder, Sticker reminders	RCT (cluster-randomized, 9 groups, 3 in SMS arm, 3 in sticker arm, 3 in control) [3]	Multivariate analysis of missed vaccination - intervention from 10 to 40% less likely to miss vaccination than control (Adjusted OR: 0.196; 95% CI 0.09 to 0.43, p-value <.001).
Uddin et al. (2016)*	Bangladesh, Rural	518-522	Mobile registration and SMS reminder, remind health workers, provide information to health worker supervisors	Quasi-experimental, pre-post (clustered, 160 clusters) [1]	"Among all age groups, intervention effects on age-appropriate vaccination coverage were positive: DIDs +13.1–30.5% and ORs 2.5–4.6 (p < .001 in all comparisons)." (n.p)

⁷ Publications with two or more experiments are split by experiment.

⁸ Percentages rounded up to the nearest whole number. Where more than one outcome is included in the study, we note the most relevant one.

Study, publication status ⁷	Country and setting	Sample	Intervention	Methods [quality score 1 (low) to 3 (high)]	Outcomes ⁸
Gibson et al. (2017)*	Kenya, Rural	628	SMS reminder, SMS reminder and cash transfer	RCT (cluster-randomized, 4 clusters) [2]	Full immunization at 12 months - SMS + 200 Kenyan Shillings 90% vs control 82% (RR: 1.09, 95% CI 1.02 to 1.16, p-value: .014).
Kazi et al. (2018)*	Pakistan, Urban	300	SMS reminder	RCT [2]	Vaccination at 14 months - intervention 31% vs control 26% (p-value:.31).
Seth et al. (2018)*	India, Rural	370	SMS reminders, SMS reminders + compliance-linked incentives.	RCT [2]	Immunization coverage at end of study - automated reminders with compliance-linked incentives intervention 44% vs control 33% (aRR: 1.09, 95% CI 1.002 to 1.18, p-value:.04). Intervention also improved timeliness.
Dissieka et al. (2019)	Côte d'Ivoire, Rural, Semi-rural, Urban	1596	SMS or Call reminder before each scheduled facility visit vs control	RCT [3]	Attendance at Vitamin A appointment - intervention 65% vs control 41% (aOR: 5.67, 95% CI: 3.48 to 9.23, p-value <.001).
Domek et al. (2019) (follow-up study)	Guatemala, Rural and Urban	720	SMS reminder	RCT	"In intention to treat analysis, both intervention and usual care groups had high rates of visit completion, but intervention participants presented on the scheduled date more often (151 [42.2%] of 358 intervention vs. 111 [30.7%] of 362 usual care participants for visit 2, p =.001, and 112 [34.0%] of 329 intervention vs. 90 [27.0%] of 333

Study, publication status ⁷	Country and setting	Sample	Intervention	Methods [quality score 1 (low) to 3 (high)]	Outcomes ⁸
Ekhaguere et al. (2019)	Nigeria, Semi-rural	600	Automated call and text immunization reminders	RCT [2]	<p>usual care participants for visit 3, $p = .05$.)”</p> <p>“At 18 weeks, 257 (86%) and 244 (81%) (risk ratio (RR) 1.05, 95% CI 0.98 to 1.13; $p = 0.15$) in the intervention and control groups received Penta-3 vaccine. At 12 months, 220 (74%) and 196 (66%) (RR 1.12, 95% CI 1.01 to 1.25; $p = .04$) in the intervention and control groups received the measles vaccine. Infants in the intervention group were more likely to receive Penta-3 (84% vs 78%, RR 1.09, 95% CI 1.01 to 1.17; $p = .04$), measles (73% vs 65%, RR 1.13, 95% CI 1.02 to 1.26; $p = 0.02$) and all scheduled immunisations collectively (57% vs 47%, RR 1.13, 95% CI 1.02 to 1.26; $p = .01$) within 1 week of the recommended date.”</p>
Kawakatsu et al. (2020)	Nigeria, Urban	8,337	SMS Reminders	RCT	<p>“The return rate for child vaccinations in the intervention group was significantly higher ($p < .001$) by 4.8% - 6.0% than that in the control group, consistently across all the five different timings (on time as scheduled, and by 7 days, 14 days, 30 days, and 3 months after</p>

Study, publication status ⁷	Country and setting	Sample	Intervention	Methods [quality score 1 (low) to 3 (high)]	Outcomes ⁸
					appointment dates). (...) The incremental recurrent cost was estimated at 7.90 US Dollars per return case."
Ibraheem et al. (2021)	Nigeria	560 mother-infant pairs	SMS reminders, phone call reminders and SMS health education, routine care	Quasi-experimental, pre-post [1]	Immunization completion at nine months - calls intervention 99% vs control 90% (aOR 8.78, 95% CI: 6.10 to 12.63, p-value <.001).
Kagucia et al. (2021)	Kenya	537	SMS reminders, SMS reminders plus a 150 Kenya Shillings incentive, control.	RCT [1]	MCV1 timely coverage - SMS + 150 Kenya Shillings intervention 78% vs control 68% (aRR: 1.16, 95% CI 1.01 to 1.32, p-value:.035).
Mekonnen et al. (2021)	Ethiopia, Urban	434	SMS Reminder	RCT [2]	Full immunization - intervention 83% vs control 71%, RR: 1.17, 95% lower CI 1.07, p-value:.002. Intervention also improved timeliness.
Buttenheim et al. (2022)	United States	11188	SMS reminder with Ownership message vs Control vs "Available" Message	RCT [3]	"Changes in vaccination rates in response to the reserved message did not reach statistical significance (increase of 1.4 percentage points, or 4% [P = .31]) compared with the message conveying that influenza vaccines were available. Relative to the usual care control, the reserved message increased vaccination rates by 3.3 percentage points, or 11% (P = .004)".

Study, publication status ⁷	Country and setting	Sample	Intervention	Methods [quality score 1 (low) to 3 (high)]	Outcomes ⁸
Yunusa et al. (2022)	Nigeria	541	3 LGAs to Reminders, 3 to Control	Quasi experimental	"Completion rates for the three doses of the pentavalent vaccine were observed to be higher for children in the reminder group (n = 161, 59.4%) compared to those in the control group (n = 92, 34.1%)."
Howell-jones et al. (2023)	United Kingdom	21,786	Behaviourally-informed invitation letter by post with minimal local adjustments.	RCT [3]	"The proportion of two- and three-year olds in each practice who received a vaccination by 31st January 2017 was 23.4% in the control group compared to 37.1% in the intervention group (OR = 1.93; 95% CI = 1.82, 2.05, p < .001)."
Howell-jones et al. (2023)	United Kingdom	1108 schools and 3010 school years in the analysis	Behaviorally informed letter, standard letter, reminder, no reminder	RCT with a 2 (behavioral letter vs. standard letter) × 2 (reminder vs no reminder) factorial design [2]	"In the standard-letter-no-reminder arm, an average of 61.6% of eligible children in each school year were vaccinated, compared to 61.9% in the behavioural-letter-no-reminder arm, 63.5% in the standard-letter-plus-reminder arm, and 62.9% in the behavioural-letter-plus reminder condition, F(3, 2990) = 2.68, p = .046."

* CE previous analysis

Other evidence

We are also encouraged by the early-stage success of Suvita, a CE-incubated charity that supports vaccination efforts in two Indian states through vaccination ambassadors and SMS reminders. Suvita is likely highly cost-effective, and we believe it has achieved reasonable operational efficiency. One particularly encouraging aspect of their model is that it has responded to data constraints - Suvita uses different operational models for data collection in different locations, depending on the available form of necessary data. We take Suvita's experience as indicative that the intervention is tractable in some contexts.

We are also aware of growing for-profit operations in mobile communications, like Viamo, who frequently collaborate with development and governmental agencies to deliver campaigns.

4.2 Evidence that the change has the expected health effects

There is a robust scientific consensus on the value of vaccines in preventing mortality and morbidity due to vaccine-preventable diseases. We do not reconstruct this body of evidence here in depth. Table 3 shows vaccine efficacy and descriptions compiled by GiveWell from several meta-analysis sources for their report on New Incentives ([GiveWell, 2022](#)).

Table 3: Vaccines commonly included in routine immunization and their efficacy
(source: [GiveWell, 2022](#))

Vaccine	Diseases Targeted	Doses	Vaccine Efficacy
PCV	Protects against pneumococcal bacteria.	Three doses	0.58 (95% CI 0.29-0.75) for all serotypes-IPD (invasive pneumococcal disease)
DTP	DTP is a combination vaccine used against diphtheria, tetanus, and pertussis (whooping cough). It is also known as DTaP or DTwP.	Three doses	0.84 (95% CI 0.81-0.87) for acellular vaccines and 0.94 (95% CI 0.88-0.97) for whole-cell vaccines for clinical case definition of pertussis, based on combinations of vaccines containing pertussis vaccines.

Vaccine	Diseases Targeted	Doses	Vaccine Efficacy
HiB	Protects against Haemophilus influenzae type b (HiB), a bacteria responsible for severe pneumonia, meningitis, and other invasive diseases, almost exclusively in children aged less than five years.	Three doses	0.82 (95% CI 0.73-0.87) for invasive HiB disease.
Measles	Measles	One dose	0.85 (95% CI 0.83-0.87) for measles.
BCG	Tuberculosis	One dose	0.85 (95% CI 0.69-0.92) for meningeal and/or miliary tuberculosis, which are the life-threatening forms of tuberculosis.
Rotavirus	Protects against rotavirus, which is one cause of diarrhea.	Two doses	0.46 (95% CI 0.29-0.59) for severe rotavirus diarrhea in sub-Saharan Africa.

5 Expert views

We conducted four in-depth interviews with academic and implementation experts, including:

- **David Doledec and Dr. Romance Dissieka:** Regional Manager for Vitamin A Supplementation & Regional Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) Coordinator, Hellen Keller International ([Doledec & Dissieka Interview](#)).
- **Debbie Rogers:** Chief Executive Officer, Reach Digital Health
- **Nii Lante Heward-Mills:** Ghana Country Manager, Viamo.
- **Varsha Venugopal:** Co-founder, Suvita.

While views on the value of the reminder services were largely positive, opinions on who should deliver the service were mixed. In most contexts, routine services (instead of campaigns) are becoming essential for country vaccination strategies. With that, there may be an increased need for the delivery of these types of reminder services to function as a net for those individuals who fall through the cracks in routine immunizations. Views on the value of the intervention itself were very positive and aligned, with an expert noting that the private sector could deliver these services in most contexts.

Our conversations with these three organizations provided us with confidence that this intervention is tractable. Non- and for-profit organizations can deliver reminders, even in cases with poor data capability (mostly by enrolling data-gathering staff).⁹

Prior efforts have not scaled well. They have likely been affected by changing donor priorities and financing, with little paid to sustainability planning and strengthening. It seems that both these issues are tractable.

Reach's CEO, Debbie Rogers, argued that while new organizations in this space would be welcome given the vast need and scarcity of players, she advocated for a more holistic, disease-agnostic approach. She suggested that there is value in having platforms that can support the health system across many needs and accompany individuals through their different and changing needs.

Our conversation with Viamo gave us some encouragement that the private sector, through this organization and several competitors, is a strongly incentivized actor in this area of work. We think an organization may play the facilitator or technical

⁹ A nonprofit could also be partially funded through charging a fee for its services.

capacity-strengthening role between these two actors (i.e., Ministries of Health and Viamo-like companies). While we did not investigate this in-depth, the conversations with experts suggested that while tractable, this intervention faces some upstream system-level barriers regarding actual vaccination capacity, government interest, and financing.

6 Geographic assessment

6.1 Where existing organizations work

We conducted desk research to understand organizations that work in this space.

Several organizations operate in this area. As discussed above, despite the hype surrounding mobile health solutions, these rarely live up to achieving large scales (Rogers interview). Overall, a cost-effectiveness-minded and narrowly focused charity can successfully achieve high levels of cost-effectiveness. Experts noted that progress in establishing reminders and other tech-based solutions will likely be more established in Eastern and Southern Africa, given higher socio-economic development than in other African regions. Below, we detail some examples of organizations that deliver this type of service.

Table 4: Organizations working in the space

Organization	What it does	Where it works	Relevance to Geographic Assessment
Suvita	Direct delivery of vaccination ambassador and message reminders.	India (Maharashtra, Bihar).	Suvita is a CE-incubated charity. We have interviewed them during our research to understand their scaling plans. They will likely scale to other Indian states in the short term and perhaps additional countries in the medium term.
Medic	Medic develops and implements tools for digitalization for community health workers and digital health programs. Several countries work with Medic as their leading developer for digitalizing services through the Community Health Worker Toolkit.	Countries that plan to use the Medic toolkit: Kenya, Mali, Nepal, Niger, Uganda, Tanzania (Zanzibar). In Ghana and Burundi, medic deployed automation of ANC appointments. Other operations: Niger, Togo, DRC, Zimbabwe, South Africa, India, Philippines.	We think Medic is a vital contributor to digital tools in LMICs. We are confident they are trusted by several government and nonprofit partners, given their portfolio of programs. Generally speaking, it is important not to duplicate their efforts where possible.

Organization	What it does	Where it works	Relevance to Geographic Assessment
Reach	Digital health solutions, operating MomConnect Africa, a chatbot pregnancy companion delivered through WhatsApp and other platforms, and a youth sexual health digital platform.	South Africa. Plans to scale across Sub-Saharan Africa.	We are uncertain about how Reach's model compares to the proposed intervention.

Beyond the above organizations, several for-profit and non-profit developers have developed software solutions for this intervention, such as [RapidSMS](#), developed by UNICEF. Other for-profit operators have proprietary services, such as [Viamo](#) and [Dimagi](#).

6.2 Geographic assessment

To assess which countries could be promising for a new organization to work in, we conducted a [geographic assessment](#). This assessment included a weighted consideration of the following factors:

Scale

We considered the following factors to understand the scale of missed childhood vaccinations and how many people the intervention could affect [50% weight on score]:

- A country's population [5% weight on score]
- [Under Five Mortality Rate](#) [15% weight on score]
- Average percentage of surviving infants who didn't receive the final recommended dose of vaccines (which can be either the second or the third dose depending on the vaccine in a given year) for several vaccines [30% weight on score].

Neglectedness

To prioritize countries where this issue is most neglected [20% weight on score], we consider countries' Gross National Income per capita - to weigh lower income

countries higher¹⁰ - [10% weight on score], and three WHO indicators that note whether a country has taken actions to improve vaccine demand: 1. Did the country implement any strategies to address under-vaccination which was informed by results of demand-related assessments? [5% weight on score], 2. Did the country implement behaviorally informed intervention strategies to address under-vaccination, which was informed by the results of demand-related assessments? [2.5% weight on score], 3. Did the country implement service quality intervention strategies to address under-vaccination, which was informed by the results of demand-related assessments? [2.5% weight on score]

Tractability

We prioritize countries where it would be relatively easy to work in [30% weight on score]. To do so, we consider a few indices, such as the Fragile States Index (2022) [10% weight on score] and Freedom in the World (2022) [5% weight on score].

Additionally, we consider mobile phone ownership [10% weight on score] and whether the country is GAVI, the Vaccine Alliance program eligible [5% weight on score].

The geographic assessment, with our chosen weights and considerations in [section 6.1](#), led to the following shortlist of options for this intervention: Papua New Guinea, Myanmar, Nigeria, Angola, Philippines, Central African Republic, Guinea-Bissau, Guinea, Madagascar, and Indonesia.

¹⁰ Generally speaking, we think this helps us prioritise countries that have more challenging healthcare needs and relatively less financial space for healthcare.

7 Cost-effectiveness analysis

Our [cost-effectiveness analysis](#) models a hypothetical 20-year program in Angola.

7.1 Effects

Modeling the effects of additional vaccinations is complex. We drew from approaches in the literature, particularly GiveWell's analysis of New Incentives and Hellen Keller International. This approach is simplistic and likely has large error bars.

We modeled effects for each country as follows:

- 1 Vaccine Schedule.** We researched each country's vaccine schedule to understand what vaccines it provides. Angola includes Vitamin A supplementation in its schedule.
- 2 Vaccine Coverage.** Each vaccine's Coverage rate was determined, mostly drawing from WHO/UNICEF Estimates of National Immunization Coverage (WUENIC) ([WHO Immunization Data Portal, 2023](#)). We fitted post-2021 numbers. We created a scatter plot of the data to fit those values and fitted a log trendline.
- 3 Vaccine-preventable burden and risk of death, by age group, for unvaccinated people.** We took the number of deaths due to each disease for each broad age group and the number of people in the cohort for a Risk of Death (RoD) estimate. We then adjust for etiology (whether a specific vaccine-preventable pathogen is to blame) to derive an Adjusted RoD per disease and total RoD. Finally, we adjusted RoD rates to represent the risk for those not vaccinated. We also adjusted the RoD for future age groups as we think several factors will contribute to improvements in the RoD for vaccine-preventable diseases.
- 4 Vaccine Efficacy.** Baseline vaccine efficacy rates followed GiveWell ([2022](#)). We calculated the effect of full immunization on the RoD through a weighted average of each vaccine's efficacy rate weighted by the burden of the diseases that the vaccine prevents.
- 5 Reach** was approximated by drawing from live births in the country (adjusted for the neonatal mortality rate). We then adjusted this by the rate of mobile phone ownership and the proportion of births attended by skilled birth attendants to reach the number of caregiver-child pairs we could potentially reach scale.

- 6 Intervention effect.** Following our evidence review, we used a risk ratio of 1.29 on the baseline full immunization. We made a subjective estimation that of those who now reach full immunization, 30% will go from zero to full doses, and the rest will go from partial to full doses. For the latter, we believe they get about 60% of the benefit from the intervention.
- 7 Other adjustments.** We made subjective estimations, such as the number of years it would take to scale, the probability of success, and other adjustments.

The effect of the intervention is essentially a factor of the reach (5), baseline coverages (2), and the intervention's effect on the coverage (6). The benefits of becoming fully immunized are a factor of what vaccines are given (1), the efficacy of those vaccines (2), and the burden of disease specific to that country adjusted for those that do not get vaccines (3).

7.2 Costs

We modeled costs as follows:

- 1 Fixed Charity Overheads.** We kept overhead costs at the same level as the other CE reports, USD 125,000 for the first year and USD 225,000 afterward. We assume this includes staff salaries, including development and management of software if required.
- 2 Set up costs.** We believe that setting up SMS/Call operations will have upfront costs, such as regulatory registration and service fees. We estimated this cost at approximately 3,500 USD, plus a similar annual maintenance cost (USD 1,800).
- 3 Per message costs** were calculated by drawing an average of online quotes from companies that manage messaging services. These were around USD 0.07/message and USD 0.14/one-minute call. We estimated that 56% of users would be reached by voice and 44% by text.
- 4 Enumeration costs** were added to reflect the fact that it's likely some form of data collection will need to take place.
- 5 Government costs per additional full immunization** were set at USD 31 based on Ikilezi et al. ([2021](#)).

- 6 Costs for beneficiaries** mainly due to travel, were set at USD 7. Instead of counting these as intervention costs per se, they were treated as adverse effects of the intervention and converted to DALY equivalents.¹¹

7.3 Results

The resulting cost-effectiveness estimates for this intervention were USD 38 and 78 per DALY averted, with the former resulting from considering charity costs alone and the latter including additional costs to the government.

¹¹ Specifically, we followed the methodology of moral weights by [GiveWell \(2020\)](#). In this framework, an equivalence is made between a doubling of a person's income for one year and a DALY value, estimated at 0.43. By incurring travel-related costs, the beneficiaries of this intervention are assumed to have to lower their consumption by about 0.57%, corresponding to roughly 0.0036 DALYs.

8 Implementation

We believe that the specific context that a charity decides to operate in and iterative adaptations will drive the final implementation model for this idea. Initially, we think that the following is plausible:

- Assuming all costs and technical delivery of reminders as an external partner, including the development of software solutions (this is the option we model).
- Assuming all costs and management of reminders as an external partner who liaises with other sub-contractors, such as for-profit entities that operate messaging services.
- Providing extensive technical assistance (and perhaps extra staff) to ministries of health and nonprofits to deliver a national-scale reminder system in-house or through sub-contracting arrangements.

Data gathering and management may be a significant hurdle depending on the country chosen. Sound data systems will be critical to optimizing the reminder system. In particular, we envision potential functionalities such as¹²:

- Notifying of new opportunities for vaccination, including non-routine vaccination or time-saving opportunities (new camp opened closer, for instance).
- Enabling trust with caregivers by notifying them in case of stock-outs (avoiding trips for no reason, for instance), and answering common questions.
- Linking up antenatal care service users with vaccination services.
- Monitoring take-up, including message testing and follow-up in case of missed appointments.

This section summarizes our concerns (or lack thereof) about different aspects of a new charity putting this idea into practice.

Table 5: Implementation concerns

Factor	How concerning is this?
Talent	Low Concern
Access to information	Moderate-high Concern
Access to relevant stakeholders	Moderate Concern
Feedback loops	Low Concern

¹² We should note that the following are potentially useful activities. However, pursuing these activities must be carefully evaluated with the relative cost-effectiveness of expanding coverage to more children in need of immunization.

Factor	How concerning is this?
Funding	Low Concern
Scale of the problem	Low Concern
Neglectedness	Moderate Concern
Execution difficulty/Tractability	Moderate concern
Negative externalities	Low concern
Positive externalities	Low concern

8.1 Talent

We do not expect that sourcing talent for this intervention will be a significant challenge for a new organization. We believe the following backgrounds or skills would benefit the co-founding team or early hires:

- Experience working with government stakeholders (E.g., Ministries of Health).
- Experience or knowledge of health data systems and routine health service provision.
- Focus and skill on logistics and operational efficiencies.
- Monitoring and evaluation, focusing on large data monitoring.

8.2 Access

Information

Setting up and maintaining robust data systems and linking those to routine immunization data would be a key enabler for the organization's work. In several low-resource contexts, this can be particularly challenging. We believe that an organization could develop workarounds for poor data availability and would encourage an organization to prioritize data access and robustness, yet still note that poor or unreliable access to this type of information may be a limiting factor for an organization in this field.

Relevant stakeholders

This intervention requires strong collaboration with routine immunization providers such as ministries of health or nonprofits. In our experience with CE-incubated organizations, accessing these stakeholders and developing relationships has not been a significant challenge.

8.3 Feedback loops

Beyond the data concerns detailed above, we do not expect monitoring and evaluation systems to be particularly challenging for this work.

8.4 Funding

Funding from funders in the CE network

GiveWell has funded immunization demand interventions such as Charity Science Health (which merged with Suvita) and New Incentives. Given the presumptive cost-effectiveness of vaccination and the scale of under-vaccination, we think additional funding would likely be available.

Broader funding sources

We are unsure about the funding landscape in this particular space. Generally speaking, experts' indications indicate an appetite for mHealth interventions in development. Debbie Rogers suggested that funders seek less fragmentation and thus may prefer to fund more holistic efforts (see [section 5](#)). Covid-19 derailed routine vaccination efforts, and there seems to be an appetite for renewed political support and financing for immunization support ([Boum, 2021](#)).

8.5 Scale of the problem

Under-vaccination is still a significantly large issue across several countries. Not all countries that suffer from under-vaccination would benefit from this specific intervention, as several factors play into this issue. However, with continuing growth in mobile phone ownership across several countries and the robustness of vaccination and its health benefits, we think the scale of the problem is large.

8.6 Neglectedness

We are uncertain about the relative neglectedness of this idea. Specifically, it is difficult to know how many governments and nonprofits who deliver routine services are actively working on developing reminder and other mobile messaging systems to bolster their service delivery. However, experts suggested that very few countries and organizations operate at a large scale.

8.7 Tractability

We do not think this intervention is particularly complicated. However, challenges around primary data collection may lead to burdensome operations and reduced cost-effectiveness.

8.8 Externalities

We do not have any significant concerns about negative externalities for this intervention. If the organization manages to set up a successful platform and trust with users, it could expand to other areas of health.

9 Conclusion

Overall, our view is that childhood vaccination reminders and encouragement is an idea worth recommending to future non-profit founders.

We are particularly excited about the prospects of establishing collaborations between a new enterprise and Suvita, which shows early signs of promise.

Simple SMS or voice reminders can be all that is necessary for a caregiver to take their child to get vaccinated, protecting them from fully preventable diseases. In this way, organizations that deliver this type of service at scale can achieve excellent impact cheaply, supporting a critical healthcare goal for low-income countries worldwide.

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